

On the Study of the Coseparation of Thorium (UX_1) with Calcium Oxalate

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The uptake of thorium (UX_1) and yttrium by calcium oxalate has been studied. It has been found that similar to rare earths, thorium (UX_1) is also carried through mixed crystal formation by calcium oxalate dihydrate. The range of mixed crystal formation of europium, yttrium, and thorium (UX_1) as guest in this system has been investigated. In the case of thorium (UX_1), an unstable guest component is carried through mixed crystal formation by calcium oxalate dihydrate.

The study of the coseparation of rare earths with calcium compounds has already been reported^{1,2}. It has been shown that some unstable modification of calcium oxalate¹ and an unstable form of calcium sulphate², during the course of precipitation, take up rare earths through mixed crystal formation. Mixed crystal formation of alkaline earth fluorides with thorium, yttrium, and rare earth fluorides³⁻⁶ has been studied in some details. The question naturally arises whether thorium is also taken up through mixed crystal formation by the same unstable form of calcium oxalate. The present investigation therefore deals primarily with the study of the uptake of UX_1 with calcium oxalate dihydrate. In the previous paper² the range of mixed crystal formation on the uptake of europium and yttrium activities by calcium oxalate dihydrate was not studied. The study of the range in these two cases has also been included as a subsidiary part of the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents used, such as, calcium chloride, acetic acid, etc., were all of AnalaR quality. UX_1 , which was used as the radioactive indicator for thorium, was isolated from aged uranyl nitrate solution by carrying it with calcium oxalate⁷. Calcium was removed by scavenging out UX_1 with $Fe(OH)_3$. Iron was subsequently removed by continuous extraction with isopropyl ether. Carrier-free Y^{91} was supplied by A.E.R.E., Harwell, England. Eu^{152} & Eu^{154} were prepared by (n, γ) reaction upon natural europium by them, using europium of spectroscopically pure quality as supplied by Messrs. Johnson & Mathey.

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2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 759.
3. Khriopin and Merkulova, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, S S S R*, 1949, **65**, 861.
4. *Ibid.*, 1950, **71**, 689.
5. Zintl and Udgard, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, **240**, 150.
6. Ketelaar and Willems, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1937, **56**, 29.
7. Purkayastha and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 427.

Two different precipitation procedures were taken recourse to in our studies: (a) Slow precipitation technique, where calcium oxalate was precipitated from a homogeneous solution by the slow release of oxalate ions through the hydrolysis of ethyl oxalate. (b) Rapid precipitation process, where the precipitation was conducted in the usual way by the rapid addition of the precipitating agent to a solution of calcium chloride. Experimental details are the same as described earlier¹. Homogeneous and heterogeneous distribution coefficients (D and λ) were calculated from the following expressions⁸⁻⁹.

$$\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solid}} = D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solution}}$$

$$\text{Log } \frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}} = \lambda \text{ log } \frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}}$$

TABLE 1*

Coprecipitation of thorium (UX₁) by calcium oxalate formed by the addition of oxalic acid to a solution of calcium chloride in acetic acid medium.

% Calcium pptd.	% Thorium (UX ₁) copptd.	λ .	D .
Initial Th conc. = $2.57 \times 10^{-6} M$.			
Initial Ca conc. = $8.725 \times 10^{-1} M$.			
A. Temp. = 35°.			
0.44	7.03	16.7	17.1
1.04	15.60	16.8	18.1
2.21	34.00	20.5	22.8
3.62	49.20	18.4	25.8
4.36	57.00	19.0	29.1
Av. 18.3			
B. Temp. = 35°.			
2.37	39.7	20.9	27.1
3.23	43.7	17.6	23.3
4.10	50.1	16.0	23.5
4.94	65.9	21.2	37.2
Av. 19.1			
C. Temp. = 40°.			
1.45	25.8	20.3	23.6
2.24	36.2	19.9	24.6
3.05	49.8	22.2	31.5
3.81	52.5	19.1	27.9
Av. 20.4			

*In experiments (B) and (C) aged uranyl nitrate solution served as the source of UX₁. In each case calcium oxalate was precipitated in presence of 81.8 mg. uranium per 25 ml of the solution in acetic acid medium.

8. Henderson and Kraoek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 738.

9. Doerner and Hoskins, *ibid.*, 1925, 47, 662.

TABLE II*

The carrying of thorium (UX₁) by calcium oxalate precipitated in ammoniacal medium at 35°.

Initial Th conc. = $1.28 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Initial Ca conc. = $4.36 \times 10^{-1} M$.

% Calcium pptd.	% Thorium (UX ₁) copptd.	λ .	D.
0.34	75.3	434.0	894
1.10	74.7	124.0	266
2.43	78.1	61.7	143
5.00	80.5	43.9	102

* Polyethylene appliances were used to guard against adsorption of activity by glass from ammoniacal solution.

TABLE III*

Coprecipitation of thorium (UX₁) with calcium oxalate by the slow release of oxalate ions through the hydrolysis of ethyl oxalate in acetic acid medium at 40°.

Initial Th conc. = $1.28 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Reaction time.	% Calcium precipitated.	% Thorium (UX ₁) coprecipitated.	λ .	D.
A. Initial Ca conc. = $8.72 \times 10^{-1} M$.				
12 hr. 30 min.	1.33	14.9	12.1	13.0
13 30	1.85	35.1	23.2	28.7
15	2.49	45.7	24.1	33.0
18	3.26	69.1	35.4	66.4
B. Initial Ca conc. = $4.36 \times 10^{-1} M$.				
4	1.24	34.2	33.7	41.4
5	2.01	54.0	38.3	57.2
5 57	2.85	72.0	43.9	87.6
6 50	3.82	87.3	53.0	173.0
7	5.95	98.7	70.7	1200.0

* Experimental observations in series (B) were carried out in presence of 81.8 mg. uranium in the total volume (50 ml) of the solution. Ethyl oxalate used in both the sets of experiments (A) and (B) was the same, viz., 5.4 g. in the total volume (50 ml) of the solution.

TABLE IV*

Coprecipitation of yttrium (Y⁹¹) with calcium oxalate formed by the addition of oxalic acid to a solution of calcium chloride in acetic medium at 35°.

Initial Y⁹¹ conc. = $1.72 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Initial Ca conc. = $8.725 \times 10^{-1} M$.

% Calcium pptd.	% Yttrium (Y ⁹¹) copptd.	λ .	D.
1.05	18.5	19.3	21.4
1.77	27.1	17.6	20.6
2.20	36.8	20.5	25.9
3.94	49.9	17.3	24.3
6.16	67.8	17.9	32.1
Av. 18.5			

* The initial concentration of the tracer ion (Y⁹¹) in solution was so chosen that it lay in the region where the λ values were found to slope down in the λ vs. concentration curve (vide Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

It was pointed earlier¹ that Kohlschütter¹⁰ had made a thorough study of the different hydrates of calcium oxalate. He showed that in acetic acid medium calcium oxalate was precipitated as the dihydrate and in ammoniacal medium it was precipitated as the trihydrate. Both these phases are, however, unstable and ultimately converted into the stable monohydrate.

Table I shows that, when calcium oxalate is precipitated in acetic acid medium, the distribution of the tracer into the host lattice follows Doerner-Hoskin's logarithmic distribution law. If the precipitation is conducted in slightly ammoniacal medium at the same temperature by the addition of ammonium oxalate solution to a solution of calcium chloride, the uptake of UX_1 (Table II) does not follow any distribution law. The conclusion can therefore be arrived at that calcium oxalate trihydrate does not take up thorium through mixed crystal formation, but it is the dihydrate which takes up thorium through mixed crystal formation, as has been observed with rare earths in our previous study¹.

When the oxalate ion is supplied through the slow hydrolysis of ethyl oxalate, the incorporation of thorium (UX_1), though the initial concentration of thorium was taken the same as it was in the case of precipitation by addition of oxalic acid, does not follow either the homogeneous or the heterogeneous distribution law (Table III). From this point of view, the uptake of thorium, however, differs from that of rare earths¹. The constancy of λ , both in conventional precipitation procedure and in precipitation through slow hydrolysis in the case of rare earths¹, is an evidence that the host lattice probably retains its structure even in hydrolytic procedure, which is about sixty times slower than the former method. Discrepancy in the case of thorium (UX_1) may lead to infer that the guest species, which is carried by calcium oxalate dihydrate through mixed crystal formation, is very unstable.

When, however, calcium oxalate is precipitated by the conventional procedure, the rate of precipitation is comparatively rapid. Before the guest species gets any opportunity to change its phase, these are entrapped by successive layers of the host lattice, which offers covering protection, and as a result, the heterogeneous distribution factor becomes constant. When ethyl oxalate serves as the source of oxalate ions in solution, the rate of growth of crystals, as has already been stated, is rather slow. The time lag in the deposition of successive layers is therefore conceivable. The unstable guest species probably breaks down before it gets any covering protection from the next successive layers. The uptake in this case therefore does not follow the distribution laws.

A comparative study of uptake (*vide infra*) may, however, serve as an indirect evidence to what has been said above as regards the uptake of thorium (UX_1) by calcium oxalate. The extent of uptake, in the case of rare earths¹, in the conventional precipitation procedure is much lower than that in the procedure through slow hydrolysis. In the case of thorium, the uptake is, however, near about of the same order in both the procedures (Tables I and III). This behaviour can be explained on the supposition that the guest species, which is taken up by a particular layer at the time of formation of the host, is

10. Kohlschütter and Marti, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 929.

eluted due to morphological changes before the arrival of the next successive layer to give it a covering protection.

In order to study the effect of increasing amounts of inactive thorium on the nature of uptake, the same amount of calcium was taken. Almost the same quantity of calcium oxalate was precipitated in each case in acetic acid medium. All other operations were conducted under identical conditions. Only the concentration of the stable tracer was varied. Similar studies were carried out in the case of europium and yttrium as well. The results are represented in Fig. 1,

(c = Initial concentration of Yttrium, europium or thorium in moles per litre)

FIG. 1. Effect of increasing amounts of tracers on the distribution factor (λ) in the system $T\text{-CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where T stands for Y, Eu or Th

which shows that the values of the heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) remain constant upto a certain concentration of inactive rare earths or thorium, above which the values of the distribution factors go on decreasing and the respective depression in λ values follows a straight line course. It must be clarified that in the region of decreasing λ values (Fig. 1), the λ values as computed from different fractions at a particular concentration of the guest are, however, constant (Table IV). Various factors may be attributed to such a behaviour where the oxalate-ion concentration, in comparison to that of the rare earths and thorium, is very high. One may conceive of the existence of different complex ions¹¹⁻¹⁴ at finite concentration and as a result, the

contribution due to the guest species that are responsible for mixed crystal formation becomes less as we go on increasing the concentration of the tracer ion.

Both in our previous work¹ and in the present work, it has been demonstrated that an unstable host lattice takes up tracer amounts of rare earths and thorium through mixed crystal formation. The nature of the guest lattice, which penetrates through mixed crystal formation, may also be unstable. The evidence of an unstable guest lattice in the process of coseparation is rather very difficult to put forth. The role of an unstable guest species can always be envisaged in such a type of anomalous mixed crystal formation and in our study on the uptake of thorium, some evidence on the existence of unstable guest species has been obtained.

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